

Determinants of Foreign Direct Investments: The Case of Ghana

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Abstract

the study assessed the determinants of foreign direct investment inflows into Ghana. It used data sourced from World Development Indicators from 1996 to 2018 in time series. The study employed OLS and FMOLS for its statistical analysis. In essence, it concluded that research and development negatively and significantly influence foreign direct investment inflows while human development and institutional quality positively and significantly influence foreign direct investment inflows. On the other hand, economic growth, inflation rate, corporate tax, and unemployment rate have no significant influence on foreign direct investment inflows. The study recommends that policymakers should strengthen and safeguard institutional regulations that would support the private sector to attract more investment to support the growth agenda. Also, human development investment ought to prioritize developing the country's human capital to augment the growth-agenda.

Keywords: Foreign direct investment; Ghana; Ordinary least square; Fully modified ordinary least square; Determinants

1. Introduction

In a market economy, foreign direct investment is considered one of the determinants of economic growth and development. Primarily, foreign direct investment is a significant factor in determining economic growth and technological advancement. In essence, it encompasses the swift and proficient transfer and adoption of standard practice across all divides (Kok & Ersoy, 2009). Foreign direct investment is prominent in economic development; hence it has garnered more attention from scholars and is widely used in enormous economic literature. Its eminence transcends to alleviate the disadvantaged plights because it elevates the standard of living of the host country's citizens and serves as a prospect for economic progress and development (Janicki, 2004; Yushang et al., 2019).

Theoretically, Dunning (1981) expatiates that the determinants of foreign direct investment rely on three essential advantages. These advantages are outlined in the eclectic theory proposed by Dunning (1981). The theory presupposes that foreign entities enter host countries for ownership, internationalization, and location advantages. Therefore, by locating in a particular country, the foreign investor expects to have an economic advantage, social advantage, and political advantage. For economic advantage, foreign investors envisage; economic stability, market size, geographical location, infrastructure etc. on the other hand, social advantage curtails language and cultural proximity while political advantage means free trade, political stability, pro-investment policies etc.

Despite the numerous benefits of FDI to the global economy, it was estimated to reduce by 40% in 2020 thus, from US\$ 1.54 trillion in 2019 to less than US\$ 1 trillion (B&FT, 2020). This phenomenon affects every country worldwide. With Ghana, not exception, foreign direct investment declined in the first and second quarter of 2020, which saw a shrink in 2019 value of about US\$ 3 billion to about US\$ 1.3 billion in the first quarter of 2020 and US\$ 437 million in the second quarter of 2020, respectively (Trading Economics, 2020). However, it is optimistic that FDI into Ghana will escalate in no time.

Figure 1 FDI Inflow from 2017 to 2020 Source: TradingEconomics.com

Even though there are numerous studies concerning the determinants of foreign direct investment inflow into Ghana, these studies' findings are inconclusive hence the need to delve into the subject matter. However, this present study intends to ascertain the determinants of foreign direct investment inflows into Ghana from 1996 to 2018 by applying economic techniques such as the ordinary least square regression method and fully modified regression method for robustness conclusion. The study would provide insight into the current determinants of foreign direct investment inflow into Ghana for policy direction and academic perusal.

The present study is divided into five-folds; thus section one, which introduces the study; section two presents the literature review; section three presents the methodology and data of the study; section four outlines the findings result, and section five concludes the study.

2. Literature Review

In determining the factors that contribute to foreign direct investment inflows into a country, several studies have been conducted to unravel the homogenous implications concerning the factors affecting FDI inflows. That notwithstanding, Reenu and Sharma (2015) studied the possible determinants of FDI in India after their economy's liberalization. Their study encompassed annual data from 1991 to 2010 and applied econometric approaches such as the ordinary least square method and others. Their findings concluded that interest rate, market size, inflation, and trade openness are the possible determinants of foreign direct investment inflows in India. Their study supported a previous study conducted by Kaur and Sharma (2013). They also found that inflation and market size are determinants of foreign direct investment inflow but, they revealed that forex reserves are another determinant of FDI inflows.

In a panel study of 20 developed and developing countries, Saini and Singhania (2017) contended that per capita income, GDP growth, commercial interest rates, domestic inflation, external debt, and trade openness are the fundamental determinants of foreign direct investment. Their study spanned from 2004 to 2013 and used dynamic and static modeling. A recent study conducted by Asiamah et al. (2018) contended that, in Ghana, electricity production, gross domestic product, and telephone usage positively determine foreign direct investment inflows both in the short-run and long-run effect. On the contrary, interest rate, inflation rate, and exchange rate negatively determine foreign direct investment inflows, both in short-run and long-run effects. However, they suggested that some mechanisms ought to be initiated to attract more FDI. It will support the growth of the economy to improve the standard of living of the citizens. However, Bobenić

Hintošová et al. (2018) share an opposing view in that innovation output, unemployment rate, inflation rate, and GDP per capita have no significant influence in attracting foreign direct investment; hence trade openness, corporate tax, and research and development negatively influence the inflows of foreign direct investment while the share of the educated labor force and level of gross wages positively influence foreign direct investment inflows.

The argument concerning the determinants of foreign direct investment inflows is indifferent and inconclusive. Therefore, this present study finds it essential to delve into the subject-matter to unravel the underlying factors that could determine foreign direct investment inflows into Ghana.

3. Method and Data

3.1 Method

To estimate the parameters of the study's variables, some econometric techniques are employed: (i) unit root test, (ii) cointegration test, (iii) correlation matrix, (iv) Ordinary least square regression method, and (v) fully modified ordinary least square regression method.

Firstly, the variables are transformed into their natural logarithm, and subsequently, unit root tests are performed. In that regard, Levin, Lin & Chu (2002), Im, Pesaran & Shin (2003), and Maddala & Wu (1999) unit root tests were performed. Evidence of unit root implies that any further attempt to perform the regression analysis would be termed as spurious hence the null hypothesis of unit root is expected to be rejected at 5% significance or less. After the variables have shown stationarity, a cointegration test must be performed to check for the cointegration or long-run relationship among the variables, thus the dependent variable against the independent variables. However, evidence of the cointegration relationship is expected to be accepted at 5% significance level. In that regard, unrestricted cointegration rank test, thus Trace test and Max-Eigen test, were performed. Furthermore, the correlation matrix is computed to ascertain the correlation between the dependent and the independent variables. Also, to check for multicollinearity, in case two or more independent variables are highly correlated with the dependent variable with coefficients of -0.70 , there is evidence of multicollinearity in the model.

Secondly, after all the pre-tests are performed to ensure the validity of the selected variables and data, the next step is to estimate the parameters' coefficients. However, the ordinary least square regression method is selected as the primary method to perform the regression analysis. Since the data is normally distributed, OLS is entirely appropriate, but it also presents some limitations such as serial correlation, endogeneity, and heterogeneity. Therefore, it is recommended that the fully modified ordinary least square regression method can resolve that problem and be regarded as the best method for small samples (Pedroni, 2000; 2001). In essence, the FMOLS is used to robustly check the primary regression method, thus the ordinary least square regression method.

Model specification

$$\ln fdi_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln gdp_t + \beta_2 \ln infl_t + \beta_3 \ln trade_t + \beta_4 \ln ume_t + \beta_5 \ln hdi_t + \beta_6 \ln Ctax_t + \beta_7 \ln R\&D_t + \beta_8 \ln IQ_t + \varepsilon_t$$

In the model, $\ln fdi_t$ represents foreign direct investment inflow as the dependent variable, $\ln gdp_t$ represents economic growth, $\ln infl_t$ represents inflation, $\ln trade_t$ represents trade openness, $\ln ume_t$ represents unemployment rate, $\ln hdi_t$ represents human development index, $\ln Ctax_t$ represents corporate tax, $\ln R\&D_t$ represents research and development and $\ln IQ_t$ represents institutional quality. β_0 represents the coefficient of the intercept, β_1 to β_8 represent the coefficients of the parameters expected to be estimated.

3.2 Data

This present study used data sourced from the World Bank's World Development Indicators and Worldwide Governance Indicators for 23 years, thus 1996 to 2018. The details for the variable are presented in table 1 below.

Table 1 Variables description

Indicators	Variable descriptions	Data Source
LNGDP	Gross domestic product per capita, constant prices	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
LNINFL	Inflation, average consumer prices	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
LNFDI	Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$)	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
LNTRADE	Trade (% of GDP)	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
LNUME	Unemployment, total (% of the total labor force) (modeled ILO estimate)	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
HDI	Human development index (HDI)	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
LNCTAX	Profit tax (% of commercial profits)	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
LNR&D	Scientific and technical journal articles	World Bank Development Indicators, World Bank
IQ	Institutional quality: Corruption control, political stability and absence of terrorism, regulatory quality, the rule of law, voice and accountability and government effectiveness: Measures on scores of +2.5 thus strong, -2.5 thus weak	Worldwide Governance Indicators, World Bank

4. Empirical findings and discussion

4.1 Summary statistics

Table 2 presents the summary statistics of the variables. From the table, it can be reported that the data is in normal distribution because the Jarque-Bera test confirms probability higher than 0.05 except LNR&D, which shows the probability of 0.023. On the other hand, the standard deviations exhibit homogenous relations among the variables. To report the mean of the variables, the table outlines that the average growth rate of FDI for the sample period was 20.347% annually, economic growth grew at an average of 0.961% annually, inflation rate increased by 2.706% annually, trade grew at 4.389% annually, the unemployment rate grew at 1.838% yearly, the corporate tax increased by 1.777% annually and research and development grew at 4.824% yearly. Moreover, human development had an average score of 0.530 index score per annum, and institutional quality deteriorated at -0.025 index score per annum.

Table 2 Summary statistics

	LNFDI	LNGDP	LNINFL	LNR&D	LNTRADE	LNUME	IQ	HDI	LNCTAX
Mean	20.347	0.961	2.706	4.824	4.389	1.838	-0.025	0.530	1.777
Median	21.048	0.948	2.698	5.480	4.325	1.836	-0.012	0.530	2.868
Maximum	21.972	2.440	3.795	7.151	4.754	2.338	0.116	0.592	3.211
Minimum	17.892	-0.564	1.902	0.000	4.122	1.425	-0.246	0.474	0.000
Std. Dev.	1.587	0.721	0.475	2.367	0.181	0.267	0.119	0.044	1.459
Skewness	-0.229	-0.336	0.373	-1.383	0.435	0.282	-0.607	0.080	-0.437
Kurtosis	1.257	3.180	2.837	3.435	2.062	2.149	2.044	1.415	1.203
Jarque-Bera	3.113	0.465	0.560	7.514	1.570	0.999	2.290	2.433	3.827
Probability	0.211	0.793	0.756	0.023	0.456	0.607	0.318	0.296	0.148
Observations	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23

4.2 Unit root tests

Table 3 exhibits the results of the unit root test executed. At level form, only one out of the four tests shows that the variables are stationary; hence there is no unit root. Furthermore, the tests were performed at the first difference; apparently, all the tests confirmed stationarity at a 1% significance level. Therefore, the assumption that there is a unit root in the variables is rejected.

Table 3 Unit root tests

Group unit root test: Summary			
Level Form			
Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Significance
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-0.742	0.229	
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.450	0.074	
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	29.272	0.045	**
PP - Fisher Chi-square	24.307	0.145	
First Difference			
Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Significance
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-10.076	0.000	***
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-9.438	0.000	***
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	108.684	0.000	***
PP - Fisher Chi-square	124.187	0.000	***

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level.

4.3 Cointegration test

Table 4 presents the cointegration test results. According to the table, there is evidence of a cointegration relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. Therefore, there is a long-run relationship between the variables. At none to at most 4, the trace test confirms that the variables are cointegrated. At none to at most 1, the Max-Eigen test also confirms that the variables cointegrated at 1% and 5% significance levels, respectively.

Table 4 Cointegration test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test							
Test (Trace)			(Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized	Trace	Sig.	Hypothesized	Max-Eigen	Sig.		
No. of CE(s)	Statistic	Prob.**	No. of CE(s)	Statistic	Prob.**		
None *	315.753	0.000	***	None *	112.919	0.000	***
At most 1 *	202.834	0.000	***	At most 1 *	55.879	0.021	**
At most 2 *	146.955	0.001	***	At most 2	38.981	0.242	
At most 3 *	107.974	0.006	**	At most 3	33.382	0.233	
At most 4 *	74.592	0.020	**	At most 4	27.218	0.252	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level.

4.4 Correlation Matrix

Computing for correlation matrix has two purposes, (i) to establish the correlation between the dependent and the independent variables and (ii) to check for multicollinearity in the variables. Table 5 below presents the outcome of the correlation matrix. No multicollinearity was witnessed because the variable with the highest correlation coefficient is LNUME, thus -0.678, below the correlation threshold to regard as collinearity. Therefore, the study could confidently reject the assumption that there is evidence of multicollinearity. A positive correlation was witnessed between LNR&D, LNGDP, IQ, HDI, LNCTAX, and LNFDI, but LNGDP has an insignificant correlation with LNFDI. On the other hand, a negative correlation was found between LNINFL, LNTRADE, LNUME, and LNFDI at a 1% significance level.

Table 5 Correlation Matrix

Correlation	LNFDI	LNGDP	LNINFL	LNR&D	LNTRADE	LNUME	IQ	HDI	LNCTAX
LNFDI	1								
LNGDP	0.139	1							
LNINFL	-0.629***	-0.405*	1						
LNR&D	0.665***	0.053	-0.496**	1					
LNTRADE	-0.660***	0.031	0.280	-0.159	1				

LNUME	-0.678***	-0.401*	0.540**	-0.575**	0.613**	1			
IQ	0.405***	0.260	-0.649**	0.830***	-0.366*	-0.664***	1		
HDI	0.540***	0.086	-0.592**	0.780***	-0.560**	-0.685***	0.757***	1	
LNCTAX	0.565***	0.194	-0.639***	0.710***	-0.607**	-0.815***	0.824***	0.855***	1

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

4.5 Results: Estimation from the ordinary least square method

Per the results in table 6, the OLS regression analysis is presented. The findings substantiate the study's objectives to ascertain the determinants of foreign direct investment in Ghana. According to the results, human development and institutional quality positively influence foreign direct investment inflows into Ghana. However, at a 1% significance level, a percentage point improvement in human development could attract 31.413% of foreign direct investment as a gross domestic product percentage. At a 5% significance level, a percentage point improvement in institutional quality could increase foreign direct investment inflows by 6.331%. It implies that the human development of Ghana serves as stimuli for attracting foreign direct investment. High human development means a highly educated and healthy labor force with a high quality of life and a proper living standard. Institutional quality is essential for development, strengthening the rule of law, voice, and accountability, implementing quality regulations for the private and public sector, ensuring political stability, controlling corruption, and government's effectiveness to ensure democratic institutions' independence positively influences foreign direct investment inflows.

Moreover, scientific and academic publications as a proxy for research and development negatively and significantly influence foreign direct investment inflows. A percentage point increase in research and development negatively significantly reduces the inflows of foreign direct investment by 0.256% at a 5% significance level. Other factors like economic growth, inflation, trade openness, unemployment, and corporate tax play an insignificant role in foreign direct investment inflows.

To check for the goodness to fitness status of the study's model, evidence from table 6 outlines that the model was fitness enough. The F-statistics showed 1% significance; the r-square suggests that the independent variables explained about 96% of the dependent variable variation, and tests for heteroskedasticity and serial correlation showed a p-value higher than 0.05.

Table 6 Ordinary least square estimation results

Dependent Variable: LNFDI						
Method: Ordinary Least Squares (OLS)						
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	Sig.	
LNGDP	-0.023	0.165	-0.142	0.889		
LNINFL	-0.063	0.245	-0.256	0.802		
LNR&D	-0.256	0.101	-2.540	0.024	**	
LNTRADE	-0.955	0.895	-1.066	0.304		
LNUME	0.439	0.695	0.632	0.538		
IQ	6.331	1.730	3.660	0.003	**	
HDI	31.413	4.707	6.674	0.000	***	
LNCTAX	-0.019	0.155	-0.122	0.904		
C	8.691	4.889	1.778	0.097	*	
R-squared	0.966	Mean dependent var		20.347		
Adjusted R-squared	0.947	S.D. dependent var		1.587		
S.E. of regression	0.367	Akaike info criterion		1.119		
Sum squared resid	1.886	Schwarz criterion		1.564		
Log likelihood	-3.872	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.231		
F-statistic	49.671***	Durbin-Watson stat		1.900		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000					

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	1.177	Prob. F(8,14)	0.377
Obs*R-squared	9.250	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.322
Scaled explained SS	4.390	Prob. Chi-Square(8)	0.820

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	0.824	Prob. F(2,12)	0.462
Obs*R-squared	2.777	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.249

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

4.6 Robust Check: Fully modified ordinary least square method

To robustly infer the findings, a fully modified ordinary least square regression method is used to check the OLS as the primary regression method robustly. Table 7 presents the results. The estimations from the FMOLS are similar to the OLS except that the coefficients differ. However, the coefficient signs are the same. Whereas LNR&D has a negative and significant sign with LNFDI, HDI, and IQ positively and significantly sign with LNFDI.

The study can robustly and statistically infer that human development and institutional quality positively determine foreign direct investment inflows in Ghana whiles research and development negatively determine foreign direct investment inflows.

Table 7 Robust check: FMOLS

Dependent Variable: LNFDI					
Method: Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS)					
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	
LNGDP	-0.040	0.115	-0.348	0.734	
LNINFL	-0.127	0.192	-0.662	0.519	
LNR&D	-0.225	0.072	-3.131	0.008	**
LNTRADE	-1.011	0.627	-1.611	0.131	
LNUME	0.441	0.494	0.892	0.389	
IQ	6.426	1.209	5.314	0.000	***
HDI	28.021	3.311	8.462	0.000	***
LNCTAX	0.019	0.108	0.173	0.866	
C	10.673	3.418	3.123	0.008	**
R-squared	0.962	Mean dependent var		20.426	
Adjusted R-squared	0.939	S.D. dependent var		1.577	
S.E. of regression	0.390	Sum squared resid		1.980	
Long-run variance	0.066				
Cointegration Test - Hansen Parameter Instability					
			Prob.*		
Lc statistic	0.933	0.050	**		

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

4.7 Granger causality test

Test for granger causality implies that the causal relationship's direction among the variables aimed to be known. Two directions are expected in the granger causality test; (i) unidirectional and (ii) bidirectional. Unidirectional signals a causal relationship from one variable to another, where the variable only causes the other but not vice versa. On the other hand, bidirectional implies that any variation in one variable causes the other variable to vice versa. The results confirm that there is unidirectional causality from inflation to foreign direct investment, unemployment to foreign direct investment, corporate tax to foreign direct investment, gross domestic product to unemployment, inflation to research and development, unemployment to inflation, inflation to institutional quality, inflation to human development, corporate tax to inflation, research and development to trade openness, research and development to unemployment, institutional

quality to trade openness, human development to trade openness, corporate tax to trade openness, unemployment to human development, institutional quality to human development, corporate tax to institutional quality and, corporate tax to human development.

A bidirectional causality was found between unemployment and trade openness.

Table 8 Granger causality test results

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests				
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	Sig.
LNINFL does not Granger Cause LNFDI	22	5.198	0.034	**
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNINFL		2.063	0.167	
LNUME does not Granger Cause LNFDI	22	11.334	0.003	**
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNUME		0.134	0.719	
LNCTAX does not Granger Cause LNFDI	22	36.017	0.000	***
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNCTAX		0.130	0.722	
LNUME does not Granger Cause LNGDP	22	2.165	0.158	
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNUME		3.368	0.082	*
LNR&D does not Granger Cause LNINFL	22	1.120	0.303	
LNINFL does not Granger Cause LNR&D		3.455	0.079	*
LNUME does not Granger Cause LNINFL	22	9.204	0.007	**
LNINFL does not Granger Cause LNUME		0.461	0.506	
IQ does not Granger Cause LNINFL	22	4.313	0.052	
LNINFL does not Granger Cause IQ		10.068	0.005	**
HDI does not Granger Cause LNINFL	22	1.668	0.212	
LNINFL does not Granger Cause HDI		4.196	0.055	*
LNCTAX does not Granger Cause LNINFL	22	3.974	0.061	*
LNINFL does not Granger Cause LNCTAX		2.559	0.126	
LNTRADE does not Granger Cause LNR&D	22	0.131	0.722	
LNR&D does not Granger Cause LNTRADE		3.747	0.068	*
LNUME does not Granger Cause LNR&D	22	0.588	0.453	
LNR&D does not Granger Cause LNUME		11.173	0.003	**
LNUME does not Granger Cause LNTRADE	22	9.065	0.007	**
LNTRADE does not Granger Cause LNUME		3.617	0.073	*
IQ does not Granger Cause LNTRADE	22	3.231	0.088	*
LNTRADE does not Granger Cause IQ		0.062	0.806	
HDI does not Granger Cause LNTRADE	22	4.360	0.051	**
LNTRADE does not Granger Cause HDI		0.046	0.833	
LNCTAX does not Granger Cause LNTRADE	22	14.482	0.001	***
LNTRADE does not Granger Cause LNCTAX		0.228	0.638	
HDI does not Granger Cause LNUME	22	0.942	0.344	
LNUME does not Granger Cause HDI		6.752	0.018	**
HDI does not Granger Cause IQ	22	1.064	0.315	
IQ does not Granger Cause HDI		4.815	0.041	**
LNCTAX does not Granger Cause IQ	22	9.185	0.007	**
IQ does not Granger Cause LNCTAX		0.084	0.775	
LNCTAX does not Granger Cause HDI	22	8.142	0.010	**
HDI does not Granger Cause LNCTAX		0.738	0.401	

Note: *** indicates 1% significance level, ** indicates 5% significance level, * indicates 10% significance level

5. Conclusion

The study aimed at identifying the determinants of foreign direct investment inflows into Ghana. Data from 1996 to 2018 were drawn from the World Development Indicators, World Bank for analysis. However, ordinary least square and fully modified ordinary least square methods were employed for the analysis. The findings of the study suggest that research and development (scientific and academic publications) negatively influence foreign direct investment inflows, and human development positively influence foreign direct investment inflows into Ghana. These findings are consistent with the study of Bobenič Hintošová et al. (2018). Moreover, institutional quality is essential in attracting foreign direct investment as the study's findings revealed that strong institutional quality devoid of corruption, political instability, and the proper institution of regulation of the private sector, strengthening of the rule of law, voice, and accountability, and government's effectiveness positively influence the attraction of foreign direct investment inflows (Vitenu-Sackey et al., 2019; Vitenu-Sackey & Alhassan, 2019). Interestingly, the findings suggest that economic growth, corporate tax, inflation rate, unemployment rate, and trade openness have no significant influence in attracting foreign direct investment into Ghana. These findings support Bobenič Hintošová et al. (2018) and Xinying et al. (2019).

The study recommends that policymakers should strengthen and safeguard institutional regulations that would support the private sector to attract more investment to support the growth agenda. Also, investment in human development ought to be prioritized to develop the country's human capital to augment the growth-agenda.

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